

SPORTS AND TOURISM ARE THE MAIN MEANS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

Djalolov Sherzod Valiyevich

PhD in philosophy in pheapagogics

Jabborov Azamjon Anvarjon o'g'li

Student of Physical Culture, Fergana State University

Phone: +99890 277-21-06

Email: sher_1557@mail.ru

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Abstract

The article broadly expresses that sport, as a fundamental element of society's culture, is one of the main means in the process of physical education through the improvement of sports skills, mastery of movement techniques, and the development of physical qualities.

Keywords

Sport, tourism, military-practical activities, tourist trips, tourism, life activity features, physical qualities, motor skills and abilities, walking, running, overcoming obstacles, and other life-practical exercises, instructor-specialist, hike.

Introduction

The word "sport" was initially understood as a game, and later it began to be seen as a means of entertainment. This is because participants were only engaging in mutual strength testing and competitions ("Main Concepts of Physical Education Theory"). Even until the late 19th and early 20th centuries, sport was viewed as a means of entertainment, relaxation, and leisure, with the goal of achieving high results or winning competitions. For a long time, it was considered insignificant in educational and developmental activities and was regarded as something unnecessary for life.

Literature review and methods

The idea that sport is a means of physical education was scientifically proven through the research of prominent scholars in the field, such as Lesgaft (1909), Ebber (1925), Gaulgoffer and Shtreyxer (1930), A.A. Ter-Ovonesyan (1978), and others.

Sport has a multifaceted meaning and is a product of social life. In society, engaging in sport is accepted as a process of physical education. As a fundamental element of societal culture, sport is one of the primary means in the physical education process through enhancing sports skills, mastering the art of movement, and developing physical qualities. It is no secret today that engaging in any type of sport provides limitless opportunities for developing motor skills in the physical education process. Evidence of this can be seen in the records being set and the results of sporting achievements.

Currently, a number of scientists in our republic, including E.Y. Davrenov, Y.F. Kuramshin, R.A. Abdumalikov, T.I. Kholdarov, B.M. Khusanboyev, L.A. Tulaganov, and others, have conducted numerous scientific studies on health promotion and physical education issues.

Regarding the physical fitness of university students, many research works have been carried out by S.P. Yevseyev, M.M. Barkoshev, A.V. Aksenov, G.A. Abramishvili, A.A. Patsuluyev, I.S. Ansupov, and others.

Results and discussion

Research aimed at improving sports results, new methodologies, tools, and enriching the content of sports training is continuously expanding. As a result, many athletes and coaches are enhancing their physical education practices with new innovative projects, theories, and methodologies based on scientific and practical principles.

Currently, tasks have been set to establish mutual friendship and solidarity with neighboring brotherly countries and to demonstrate deeper human qualities during competitions.

It was previously believed that some characteristics of sport in various social conditions are completely contradictory. This can be seen in the goals and tasks of Soviet sport and the meaning of professionalism in bourgeois sport.

In developed countries, more students, military personnel, and naval officers engage in sports. The main reason for this is that sport is a crucial factor in military and life preparedness. Moreover, in these countries, the economic role of sport occupies a leading position. They engage in sports not for relaxation, changing the form and function of the human body, but to live and create material wealth.

Because the historical development of sport has led to some of its types gaining international recognition, acquiring vital and necessary importance, and being accepted as a primary means of physical education, sports like athletics, weightlifting, classical wrestling, boxing, swimming, basketball, football, handball, tennis, cycling, volleyball, water polo, gymnastics, and other types have established national and international federations. Sports included in the program of Asian, European, World Championships, and the Olympic Games, as well as national types of sports, are considered essential means of physical education. These involve life-practical, military-practical exercises, and other sports types used in the educational process.

Tourism is a planned trip based on a schedule that involves activities such as excursions, hiking, rock climbing, and walks. It does not involve creating material goods, but rather serves as a means of developing physical abilities and qualities, as well as offering active rest. It is known from the travels of geologists and hydrogeographers that their trips are planned with the aim of creating material value. In the process of physical education, however, its specific aspects are utilized.

Tourist trips help in developing skills to overcome natural obstacles, as well as nurturing intellectual, physical, ethical, mental, and aesthetic qualities. Participants develop relations with the team, fearlessness, strength, and endurance. In these trips, the way of life in the mountains, the steppe, living conditions, labor, and the ability to adapt to the environment are developed. Tourism, in comparison to other physical education factors, differs in its practicality, environment, and conditions. It stands out for the wide variety of physical exercises it involves.

Tourism, as a means of physical education, has the following key characteristics:

1. Practicality: It fosters independent activity and initiative. It helps develop a variety of skills, such as leadership, management, goal setting, route selection, and reading maps.
2. Physical qualities: Tourism nurtures and develops all physical qualities, movement skills, and abilities equally, since it does not focus on developing traits required for a specific sport or professional training.

3. During preparation for the trip and throughout the journey, all activities of practical importance, such as walking, running, overcoming obstacles, and other life-practical exercises, are utilized.

4. No physical fitness requirement: Tourism does not require a certain level of physical fitness, which makes it similar to sport.

5. Effect of physical exercises: During tourism, physical exercises have a varying impact on the body, depending on the climate conditions (cold, heat, wind) and the relief of the route.

6. Competition: Tourism does not focus on strength testing or competition.

7. Leadership selection: In a tourist trip, participants must be able to choose a suitable leader. The leader must be at least 16 years old and experienced. The leader also participates in the trip along with the participants. They perform additional tasks: plan the tourist route, study the composition and identities of participants, inspect the equipment, and address practical issues.

If the participants of the trip are young travelers, a specialist guide who is at least 19 years old is appointed as the leader.

8. The main form of tourism activities is hiking. During a hike, all the skills, techniques, and methods that need to be learned during tourism are used. Life-essential movement skills are formed and enriched. In these activities, swimming, climbing, and other similar tasks, as well as working with topography and overcoming obstacles, are mastered. It is necessary to combine physical exercises such as overcoming natural obstacles and carrying loads with tourism activities to achieve the desired results.

Conclusion

An analysis of literature and practical experience shows that in our country and the global community, there have been no fully developed normative programs in physical education and sports tourism in recent years. This indicates that the issues in the tourism sector have not been sufficiently studied in our country, and this problem requires a solution.

In conclusion, it should be noted that from 1960 to 1990, a number of authors (A.D. Novikov, L.P. Matveyev, B.A. Ashmarin, and others) classified the exercises used in the educational process according to the characteristics of the historically formed physical education systems. However, as systems were updated and exercises used in the educational process improved, new exercises began to fail to fit into the historically accepted sets of exercises. This was because, by their nature, these new exercises were almost indistinguishable from gymnastics, games, sports, or tourism exercises.

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